

FAM_02041

BGC type: Siderophore

FAM_02041

BGC type: Siderophore

FAM_03495
BGC type: NAGGN

FAM_03495

BGC type: NAGGN

FAM_02294

BGC type: Bacteriocin

FAM_02538

BGC type: Betalactone

FAM_02538

BGC type: Betalactone

FAM_01909
BGC type: NRPS

FAM_01909
BGC type: NRPS

FAM_03455

BGC type: Bacteriocin

FAM_03455

BGC type: Bacteriocin

FAM_03064

BGC type: Bacteriocin

FAM_03064

BGC type: Bacteriocin

FAM_02938
BGC type: NRPS-like

FAM_02938

BGC type: NRPS-like

FAM_03061

BGC type: Bacteriocin

FAM_03061

BGC type: Bacteriocin

FAM_02289
BGC type: NRPS

FAM_02289

BGC type: NRPS

FAM_00383
 BGC type: NRPS-like

FAM_00383

BGC type: NRPS-like

FAM_01903

BGC type: Betalactone

FAM_01903

BGC type: Betalactone

FAM_02487

BGC type: Arylpolyene

FAM_02487

BGC type: Arylpolyene

FAM_03189

BGC type: Betalactone

FAM_03189

BGC type: Betalactone

FAM_02150
BGC type: NAGGN

FAM_02150

BGC type: NAGGN

FAM_02432
BGC type: NAGGN

FAM_02432

BGC type: NAGGN

FAM_01878
BGC type: Arylpolyene

FAM_01878

BGC type: Arylpolyene

FAM_02401
BGC type: NRPS-like

FAM_02401

BGC type: NRPS-like

FAM_02424

BGC type: NRPS

FAM_02424

BGC type: NRPS

FAM_02047
BGC type: NAGGN

FAM_02047

BGC type: NAGGN

FAM_03491

BGC type: Arylpolyene

FAM_03491

BGC type: Arylpolyene

FAM_02426

BGC type: Arylpolyene

FAM_02426

BGC type: Arylpolyene

FAM_02589

BGC type: Siderophore

FAM_02589

BGC type: Siderophore

FAM_02524
BGC type: NAGGN

FAM_02524

BGC type: NAGGN

FAM_03259

BGC type: NAGGN

FAM_03259

BGC type: NAGGN

FAM_02044

BGC type: Betalactone

FAM_02044

BGC type: Betalactone

Summary table. This table summarize the proportion of node connections that preserve totally (purple) or almost totally (blue) the evolutionary direction .

Gene Cluster Family (GCF)	Ratio of blue and purple lines / total node connections	Percentage (%)
FAM_03070	56/58	96.6
FAM_03495	43/50	86.0
FAM_02294	28/31	90.3
FAM_02538	26/30	86.7
FAM_01909	26/28	92.6
FAM_03455	26/28	92.6
FAM_03064	17/26	65.4
FAM_02938	25/25	100
FAM_03061	12/21	57.1
FAM_02289	15/20	75.0
FAM_00383	14/19	73.7
FAM_02041	19/19	100
FAM_01903	9/18	50.0
FAM_02487	18/18	100
FAM_03189	17/17	100
FAM_02150	15/16	93.8
FAM_02432	15/16	93.8
FAM_01878	12/14	85.7
FAM_02401	14/14	100
FAM_02424	14/14	100
FAM_02047	13/14	92.9
FAM_03491	13/13	100
FAM_02426	12/12	100
FAM_02589	8/12	66.7
FAM_02524	10/10	100
FAM_03259	10/10	100
FAM_02044	10/10	100